

Deliverable D4.2

Deployment of a container system (accessible from the AI4Life website)

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMZ	BioImage Model Zoo
CI	continuous integration
D	Deliverable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FOSS	Free and open-source software
GUI	Graphical user interface
HPC	high-performance computing
ML	Machine Learning
OCI	Open Container Initiative
PU	Public
RI	Research Infrastructure
v	Version
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

The AI4Life project aims to democratise modern Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods for biological imaging, building bridges between life sciences and computer vision researchers that can expand the reach of cutting-edge techniques. Work package 4 (WP4) is key in the development of contributor services that help method developers and advanced image analysts integrate reproducible deep-learning-based algorithms into the Bioimage Model Zoo (BMZ), the central project of AI4Life.

This Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2) describes the open-source tools developed within the project to containerise bioimage analysis machine learning (ML) algorithms in a way that they are reproducible across platforms and users. For this, we designed a new platform, DL4MicEverywhere^{1,2}, that automatically containerises user-oriented open-source Jupyter Notebooks using Docker (OCI³) and publishes versioned Docker images in Docker Hub⁴, ensuring the long-standing reproducibility of the methods. Complementarily, the BioEngine⁵ empowered by Hypha, can be used as a cloud-based container management system for DL4MicEverywhere containers, making them accessible from the AI4Life and Biolmage Model Zoo websites. These advancements streamline the contribution, creation, reuse, and execution of Biolmage Analysis pipelines in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.

¹ <https://github.com/HenriquesLab/DL4MicEverywhere/tree/main>

² Iván Hidalgo-Cenalmor, Joanna W Pylvänäinen, Mariana G Ferreira, Craig T Russell, Ignacio Arganda-Carreras, AI4Life Consortium, Guillaume Jacquemet, Ricardo Henriques, Estibaliz Gómez-de-Mariscal. DL4MicEverywhere: Deep learning for microscopy made flexible, shareable, and reproducible. bioRxiv 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.11.19.567606>

³ <https://opencontainers.org/>

⁴ <https://hub.docker.com>

⁵ <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/announcing-bioengine/>

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, led by the project coordinator Euro-BioImaging and participated by ten partners, four of them being European Research Infrastructures themselves. The project started in September 2022 and will continue until September 2025.

AI4Life aims to bring state-of-the-art AI-based image analysis to life scientists by establishing and supporting innovative services that target both researchers in the life sciences and computational methods developers in the AI and computer vision fields.

Work Package 4 (WP4) focuses on 'Contributor Services' and contributes to Objectives 1-3 and 5 of AI4Life:

- Objective 1: Democratise the availability of AI-based image analysis methods as a FAIR service accessible through the AI4Life service landscape and computationally powered by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure.
- Objective 2: Establish standards for the submission, storage and FAIR access of reference data, reference annotations (ground-truth), trained AI models, and trainable AI methods.
- Objective 3: Simple model deployment, sharing, and dissemination of AI-based methods as a new developer-facing service of the BioImage Model Zoo (BMZ)⁶.
- Objective 5: Empower common image analysis platforms with AI tools.

To do so, five different tasks were defined:

- Task 4.1 Establish containerisation structure and services.
- Task 4.2 Easy development and deployment of new methods.
- Task 4.3 Enable Human-in-loop BioImage Model Zoo workflow.
- Task 4.4 Continuous integration services (Automated testing).
- Task 4.5 Implement data sharing and protection guidelines.

This second deliverable (D4.2) focuses on Task 4.1 by providing a container system that allows contributors, users and developers of the BioImage Model Zoo (the central repository to interconnect the tools related to the AI models and methods) to deploy the methods and models conveniently. The containerisation system relies on the new platform DL4MicEverywhere. The platform is equipped with a continuous integration workflow that allows the automatic and tested containerisation of Jupyter Notebooks reproducing ML methods for bioimage analysis. Namely, DL4MicEverywhere features interactive Jupyter Notebooks with user-friendly graphical interfaces that require no

⁶ <https://bioimage.io/>

coding skills and are encapsulated in Docker images⁷. The platform is equipped with extended documentation for developers and users. In this document, we describe DL4MicEverywhere and how it supports the tasks and objectives of Work Package 4. Likewise, in collaboration with WP5 and WP2, we are establishing a flexible containerisation infrastructure to further improve the accessibility of AI in life science. These container repositories together with deployment toolkits aim to allow research institutes to easily replicate our computing platform for AI model serving and notebooks execution on their on-premise GPU servers and computing clusters. By enabling on-prem deployment, we make the AI models serving more sustainable, and improve the data privacy, potentially for dealing with sensitive data in healthcare.

2. Description of work

2.1 Online distribution and accessibility to containerised notebooks

Figure 1: Updated Figure 1 with respect to the deliverable D4.1. Containerisation allows for the creation of a shareable and common virtual environment to reproduce bioimage analysis pipelines.

The Biolmage Model Zoo (BMZ)⁸ is the central point for life-scientists and developers to interact with AI-models and methods within the AI4Life project. It establishes a user-friendly space to search and launch models, methods, notebooks and even find

⁷Docker images are software units that contain the virtualisation of a specific computational environment, with all the specified dependencies and packages included. Docker containers are the functional instances of Docker Images. That is to say, a Docker Image is built with all the required specifications, and from there, one can run as many Docker containers as desired with the same configuration. Docker images are portable and installable across systems. Therefore, they are highly recommended to ensure the reproducibility of computational pipelines. These images can be uploaded to Docker Hub to support the FOSS distribution. Additionally, Docker belongs to the OCI, meaning that containers are compatible with other container systems such as Singularity.

⁸ <https://bioimage.io/>

datasets to train new models. Thus, the new tools developed within WP4 are directly distributed through the BioImage Model Zoo, and the algorithms live in the BioImage.IO GitHub community (see Figure 1). DL4MicEverywhere is accessible through the BioImage Model Zoo⁹, and the Services site of the AI4Life webpage¹⁰. A documented container repository structure is indexed in the AI4Life website¹¹ as well, allowing users and research institutions to easily find and download the developed Docker Images in their infrastructures.

2.2 Software tools for the automatic containerisation of deep learning methods

Figure 2: Schematic description of the automatic containerisation proposed by DL4MicEverywhere. Developers can contribute their models within DL4MicEverywhere notebooks directly to the DL4MicEverywhere GitHub Repository. The repository runs an automatic continuous integration pipeline to test the format of the notebooks, the correct building of Docker Images and publishes a versioned Docker Image in Docker Hub. This containerisation is synchronised with the BioImage Model Zoo and follows the same specifications, ensuring that the methods are accessible to non-expert users. Non-expert users access the containerised workflows with a user-friendly graphical user interface (GUI) that automatically launches the Docker container corresponding to the operating system and configuration of the users. Once the Docker container is set up, the users can interact with the method directly in Jupyter Notebooks without dealing with the intricacies of Docker containerisation. Likewise, the users will be able to reproduce the pipelines, train their models and contribute them to the BioImage Model Zoo within a reproducible and portable ecosystem.

⁹ <https://bioimage.io/#/?partner=dl4micverywhere&type=application&id=dl4micverywhere%2Fd4micverywhere>

¹⁰ <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/dl4micverywhere/>

¹¹ <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/containers/>

DL4MicEverywhere¹² serves as an infrastructure and service for containerising deep learning methods in the context of bioimage analysis (see Figure 2). Specifically, it offers researchers an easy-to-use gateway to portable and reproducible deep learning techniques for bioimage analysis encapsulated in Docker images. The platform assists model developers by providing the tools to automatically containerise their methods, which guarantees smooth operation across various computing environments.

The platform's infrastructure and services include the following key features:

- **New standards:** DL4MicEverywhere defines new standards for the containerisation of bioimage analysis pipelines, following the BioImage Model Zoo standards. It builds upon the Resource Description File¹³ to ensure a general format and traceable versioning of the containerised workflows, notebooks, and Docker images, enhancing reproducibility and standardisation in the field.
- **Automatic containerisation of the BioImage Analysis pipelines.** The platform's backend automatically builds Docker images for AMD64 (Windows/Linux/macOS – Intel) (with and without GPU access) and ARM64 (macOS-M1/M2) systems. This process controls the versions of the required libraries upstream and downstream of the Docker container, enabling the automatic containerisation of bioimage analysis pipelines. It allows the encapsulation of Jupyter Notebooks for high-level and documented programmatic interaction, along with the necessary dependencies for method deployment.
- **Continuous integration system¹⁴:** DL4MicEverywhere incorporates an automatic validation pipeline to test the correct containerisation of machine learning pipelines. This ensures the reliability and accuracy of the containerised methods, contributing to their robustness and reproducibility.
- **Publicly available Docker images in Docker Hub¹⁵:** The platform automatically uploads validated Docker images to Docker Hub, ensuring their long-term reproducibility and accessibility. This feature enhances the availability and usability of the containerised methods for the broader research community.

The functionalities of DL4MicEverywhere are supported by a user-friendly GUI that allows users to rapidly launch the Docker containers and interact with the notebooks in a zero-code fashion (see Figure 3). This interface is designed in a way that public methods available in the BioImage Model Zoo or private and local ones can be automatically launched without dealing with the intricacies of Docker configurations, environment setups, or coding. This is enabled by the advanced mode of the user interface.

¹² <https://github.com/HenriquesLab/DL4MicEverywhere>

¹³ https://bioimage.io/docs/#/bioimageio_model_spec

¹⁴ <https://github.com/HenriquesLab/DL4MicEverywhere/tree/main/github/workflows>

¹⁵ <https://hub.docker.com/r/henriqueslab/dl4mic everywhere/>

a)

b)

Figure 3: DL4MicEverywhere interface models. a) The basic mode allows the launch of containerised notebooks that are publicly available and tested. b) Advanced options allowing for the automatic containerisation of local or private models.

Overall, DL4MicEverywhere provides a comprehensive infrastructure and service for containerising methods in bioimage analysis, aiming to set new standards, offer automated processes, and ensure the reproducibility and accessibility of deep learning techniques in this field.

2.3 Open source and user-friendly containerised notebook platform to support the interaction with AI4Life

DL4MicEverywhere builds upon ZeroCostDL4Mic to feature interactive Jupyter Notebooks with user-friendly graphical interfaces that require no coding skills. Thus, it extends the capabilities of the previous platform by allowing the execution of notebooks either locally on personal devices like laptops or remotely on diverse computing platforms, including workstations, high-performance computing (HPC), and cloud-based systems. It currently incorporates numerous pre-existing ZeroCostDL4Mic notebooks for tasks such as segmentation, reconstruction, and image translation, already containerised.

A DL4MicEverywhere notebook is a notebook to assist researchers in using deep-learning models for image processing. This notebook is fully encapsulated within a Docker image, providing a controlled and versioned snapshot of the dependencies

required for the notebook. The versions of the required libraries are controlled upstream and downstream of the Docker container. The notebook is validated using continuous integration (CI) workflows to ensure compatibility with ARM64 and AMD64 (with and without GPU access). It features a user-friendly interface similar to ZeroCostDL4Mic, allowing users to train the model, perform quality checks, and run inference on new data. Additionally, the notebook is fully traceable and open source.

The collection of containerised and validated notebooks is organised in ZeroCostDL4Mic notebooks, External notebooks and Bespoke notebooks¹⁶, providing a flexible service for the contribution of new methods and their dissemination (see Figure 4). This categorisation allows separating the notebooks based on their source and customisation needs.

Figure 4: DL4MicEverywhere accepts three types of notebook contributions: ZeroCostDL4Mic notebooks, bespoke user-friendly notebooks inspired by ZeroCostDL4Mic, and notebooks hosted in external repositories that are compliant with our format. These contributions are automatically tested to ensure the correct requirements and format.

ZeroCostDL4Mic notebooks: These are the core notebooks of the platform. At the moment, the platform contains 28 Jupyter Notebooks¹⁷ with a user-friendly graphical interface that requires no coding. This collection supports a wide array of microscopy analysis tasks, including segmentation, reconstruction, registration, and denoising, as well as novel deep learning approaches such as generative models or diffusion models.

¹⁶ https://github.com/HenriquesLab/DL4MicEverywhere/blob/main/docs/NOTEBOOK_TYPES.md

¹⁷ <https://github.com/HenriquesLab/DL4MicEverywhere/tree/main/notebooks>

Bespoke notebooks: They can leverage the full capabilities of the DL4MicEverywhere framework and are designed for specific functionalities, such as showcasing the programmatic interaction with models from the BiImage Model Zoo.

External notebooks: They enable community contribution. While the containerisation process relies on the DL4MicEverywhere backend, the notebooks can reside on its developers' GitHub repository or even the BiImage Model Zoo. Allowing developers to connect to the platform as an external contribution, allows further maintenance and update of the method while ensuring the correct containerisation. An example is the FRU-Net notebook¹⁸, available as a contribution to the BiImage Model Zoo and containerised with DL4MicEverywhere.

These exemplar containerised methods constitute a template and standards for developers to create new user-friendly reproducible and cross-compatible workflows (Task 4.1 and Task 4.2) that can be directly connected with the BiImage Model Zoo.

2.4 Containerised Jupyter Notebooks for the deployment of standard models available through the BiImage Model Zoo and AI4Life websites

The BiImage.IO Core library provides a series of example notebooks¹⁹ to guide newcomers in the deployment, consumption, export, and import of the models in the BiImage Model Zoo. These notebooks are now encapsulated within Docker containers and accessible through the BiImage Model Zoo²⁰ or the DL4MicEverywhere interface (see Figure 5). Likewise, the notebooks can be used directly in Google Colab or within developers' personal environments.

These notebooks allow us to seamlessly load models from the BiImage Model Zoo, access each of the components of the models, reproduce the programmatic testing and validation within the BiImage Model Zoo, and use the models with new images. We expect these notebooks to ease the future deployment, sharing, and dissemination of AI models.

As a complementary development, we aim to use the BioEngine to manage and deploy the DL4MicEverywhere containers in the cloud and HPCs. The BioEngine deployment toolkit will be delivered via "D2.2 Deployment kit for user institutions to replicate the cloud infrastructure (accessible from the AI4Life website)".

¹⁸ <https://bioimage.io/#/?type=application&id=deepimagej%2Fevstemsegmentationfrunet>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/bioimage-io/core-bioimage-io-python/tree/main/example>

²⁰ <https://bioimage.io/#/?type=application&tags=General%20BiImageIO>

Figure 5: Accessibility to general notebooks for the BiImage Model Zoo synchronised and accessible across platforms.

3. Conclusion

The infrastructure and service to containerise machine learning methods for bioimage analysis and the contribution of a large collection of already containerised notebooks within D4.2 constitute a bridge between computer scientists developing AI methods and the FAIR ecosystem that we are building in AI4Life. These resources give developers and new contributors the opportunity to build reproducible analytical pipelines that are compatible across systems, servers and workstations, and disseminate them through a dedicated ecosystem for life sciences. In parallel, these developments address the critical need for scalability and flexibility in computational resources of deep learning-based bioimage analysis pipelines and align with the goals of AI4Life to democratise the availability of AI-based image analysis methods as a FAIR service accessible through the AI4Life service landscape and computationally powered by the EOSC infrastructure.

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